

The influence of reading skills, critical thinking skills, and metacognition on comprehension of explanatory text: context of middle school science lessons

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ABSTRACT: Reading Skills, Critical Thinking, and Metacognition are several factors that influence students' success in taking science lessons. In general, Science, like other lessons, consists of explanatory texts that contain various information related to scientific concepts. Unfortunately, in general, the science learning outcomes of students in Indonesia, including in Jambi, are still relatively low. This research aims to determine the influence of reading skills, critical thinking, and Metacognition on understanding explanatory texts in the context of science learning. This research applies a correlational quantitative method approach. All variable data in this research was obtained through tests. The test instrument used is a set of questionnaire questions for the variables RS, CTS, and Metacognition, as well as multiple choice questions for understanding the explanatory text. The respondents involved in this research were 136 junior high school students in Jambi City. Data analysis was carried out with the help of SPSS 25 software, especially regarding statistical correlation tests between variables. Participants showed a relatively positive level of each variable (reading skills, critical thinking skills, Metacognition, and understanding of explanatory text). In addition, a strong correlation was found between reading skills (RS) and critical thinking skills (CTS), and Metacognitive Ability (MA) was significantly correlated with Explanatory Text Comprehension (PTE). The T-test results show that the correlation of each of these variables is significant. Successively, the correlation between the three variables, namely RS, CTS, and Metacognition, has different levels of correlation, namely 0.477**, 0.770**, and 0.404**, respectively. Conclusion: The T-test results show that the correlation of each of these variables is significant. Successively, the correlation between the three variables, namely RS, CTS, and Metacognition, has different levels of correlation, namely 0.477**, 0.770**, and 0.404**, respectively. Therefore, science teachers need to carry out learning that begins with effective and consistent reading activities, provide challenging questions that have the potential to trigger an increase in CTS, and assist in learning planning for students. With increasing challenges, these learning activities can be carried out synchronously and asynchronously. In the future, students will be required to read Science explanatory texts more often in recreational digital environments than in academic digital environments.

Keywords: Reading Skills, Critical Thinking Skills, Metacognition, Explanatory Text

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1. Introduction

Science is a crucial subject in almost all countries, including Indonesia. Science lessons are one of the foundations or keys to future technological development (Wang, 2021). Students' mastery of scientific concepts provides opportunities for better technological development. Therefore, various efforts continue to be made to improve mastery of scientific concepts or literacy (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017) for students since they are at the primary and secondary education levels, even since kindergarten (Ravanis, 2017).

Efforts to increase mastery of science concepts by students in Indonesia have yet to be completely successful. Several reports show that students' mastery of scientific concepts (scientific literacy) in Indonesia still needs to be higher compared to other countries, especially OECD member countries. Mayasari and Paidi (2022) reported that the results of the 2018 PISA survey showed that students' scientific literacy scores in Indonesia had decreased compared to the 2015 period. Hanifah and Retnoningsih (2019) also reported in their research that the scientific literacy abilities of Indonesian students were below the international average. A similar report was also submitted by Sutrisna (2021), stating that the scientific literacy of Indonesian students was in the low category. Official reports from the Indonesian government also state that the scientific literacy abilities of students in Indonesia still need to be optimal (Totok, 2019). Many factors cause the low level of scientific literacy skills.

From an Indonesian language learning perspective, science content is taught using explanatory texts. Descriptions of science material presented in teaching materials, both printed and electronic, are generally in the form of explanatory texts. All texts in science teaching materials fulfill the characteristics of explanatory texts as mentioned by Sari et al. (2020) and Akhir (2021), namely: (1) contains terms, (2) the sentence structure uses conjunctions that show cause and effect relationships, (3) explains conditions (explains phenomena rather than telling about the past), (4) uses sequence conjunctions /sequence. Meanwhile, Sihombing et al. (2021) and Anggeraeni et al. (2023) explain that explanatory text is a text that explains the process of a phenomenon that is related to the questions "why" and "how." According to him, the phenomena explained can be natural phenomena, for example, floods, tsunamis, earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, and others, as well as social phenomena, for example, poverty, juvenile delinquency, and corruption. Therefore, it can be under scientific material in various materials or other learning resources that generally fulfill the characteristics of explanatory texts.

As an explanatory text, studying Science (natural phenomena) can also be done using a language-learning approach. Even though these two subjects, namely Indonesian and Science, have very different characteristics (genres), both in substance and in the perception of students and teachers, they both have similarities, namely that they are presented as explanatory texts. In this way, studying both subjects can be done from the same point of view, namely, understanding explanatory texts. Unfortunately, there are not many science explanatory texts in Indonesian language lessons. In general, learning explanatory texts in Indonesian language lessons uses texts on social phenomena, for example, poverty, juvenile delinquency, and corruption, and rarely uses natural phenomena.

The use of explanatory texts in the natural phenomena genre in learning Indonesian as a reading medium, apart from being able to increase students' understanding of Indonesian language subject matter, for example, sentence structure, diction/vocabulary/terms used, and so on, can also increase students' understanding of Science. Conceptually, a reading activity is a process by someone to obtain a message the writer wants to convey through words/written language (Tahmidaten & Krismanto, 2018). Jose and Dharma (2011), Restuningsih et al. (2017), and A. Al Roomy (2022) explains that reading is the activity of searching for information/data through written symbols. Therefore,

science texts that contain messages/information/data about natural phenomena have great potential as explanatory texts that provide new nuances for teachers and students. However, unfortunately, explanation texts are not widely used by Indonesian language teachers in teaching explanatory texts.

The use of Science explanatory texts in learning to read (in the context of Indonesian language learning) is believed to be one of the factors causing students' low level of scientific literacy in Indonesia. One Indonesian education expert, Sutrisna (2021), stated that the low scientific literacy of students is caused by several factors in the education system, such as the curriculum, teachers, and students themselves. According to Latif et al. (2022), several causes of the low level of scientific literacy of students in Indonesia are due to the low quality of sources and teaching materials, non-contextual learning, and the low reading ability of students. Suparya et al. (2022) also explained that two of the causes of the low scientific literacy abilities of students in Indonesia are non-contextual learning and the low reading abilities of students. The Ministry of National Education's report regarding the implementation of PISA in 2018 also stated that besides scientific literacy, students obtained low reading scores (Totok, 2019). This fact is also in line with the opinion of Latif et al. (2022) that one of the reasons for the low scientific literacy of students in Indonesia is their low reading ability.

The relative reading ability of students in the context of reading science explanatory texts is likely to impact students' low scientific literacy and cannot be confirmed with certainty. This statement is based on the fact that no report has stated that the low level of scientific literacy - as the primary indicator of scientific ability - is caused by students' reading ability. It means that one of the causes of low scientific literacy is that low reading skills are still opinionated and have yet to be proven empirically, so they need to be proven further. Therefore, this research seeks to provide new evidence on whether reading skills influence students' understanding of science explanation texts. This evidence provides inspiration and input for Indonesian language subject teachers to implement explanatory text learning using science texts so that these subjects have the potential to support efforts to increase the scientific literacy of Indonesian children.

Studying explanatory text can not only improve understanding of the text and have the potential to improve scientific literacy skills (if the explanatory text used is scientific material) but also has the potential to improve critical thinking skills (CTS). In terms of theoretical concepts, Ebe (2022) and Lombardi et al. (2022) explain that critical thinking is an intellectual process of creating concepts, applying, synthesizing, and evaluating information obtained from observation, experience, reflection, thinking, or communication as a basis for believing and taking action. Norrisqa (2021), Craft (2022), and Oshanova et al. (2022) explain that critical thinking is a process of searching, producing, analyzing, collecting, and conceptualizing information as a reference with personal awareness and the ability to increase creativity in dealing with a problem. Thus, CTS is an intellectual thinking process to solve various problems with a scientific approach. Therefore, in learning activities, CTS is essential.

According to experts, CTS plays a crucial role in students' success in following the learning process at school. Subhash et al. (2022), Kawita (2023), and Min et al. (2023) stated that CTS plays a crucial role in students' success in learning languages. Apart from language subjects, Karakoc (2016) and Devi and Bayu (2020) stated that critical thinking skills are necessary for students to learn Science and carry out scientific activities. Thus, CTS is essential in learning from a language and science perspective. The subjects of language and Science include activities or processes of creating concepts and applying, synthesizing, and evaluating information obtained from observation or reading. Of course, what is read is explanatory text. It means that critical thinking is closely related to reading activities and is scientific. These activities are needed in learning science. Thus, critical thinking skills influence science learning and learning outcomes (scientific literacy).

Experts or researchers have widely proven the relationship between critical thinking skills (CTS) and understanding of science concepts or learning outcomes; for example, Devi and Bayu (2020) found that CTS positively affected mastery of science concepts in elementary school students. In research, Hidayati (2016) and Mohamed Nor and Sihes (2021) also prove that CTS positively influences science learning outcomes. Therefore, in science learning, CTS is an important factor for students to study Science successfully. Turan et al. (2019), Norrisqa (2021), and Kadrija et al. (2023) state that CTS is needed in learning Science because CTS is related to complex thinking or high-level thinking, of which there are four types, namely problem-solving, decision making, critical thinking, and creative thinking. Thus, critical thinking skills are an essential factor influencing low scientific literacy.

Conceptually, critical thinking is a person's objective ability to analyze problems based on available evidence and information to make decisions (Facione, 2020; Rosadi et al., 2023). Jupriyanto (2018) explains that critical thinking is a reflective ability focusing on decision-making patterns. Syofyan & Halim (2017), Rogti (2021), and Heard et al. (2020) explain that critical thinking skills have four attributes, namely: 1) analysis, the ability to solve parts of information, grouping parts of information, grouping information, and the ability to conclude, 2) attention, critical thinking will become a habit if participants students pay attention, 3) awareness, the ability to see what is happening around someone, 4) Independent Judgment or giving independent considerations, the ability to give considerations or evaluations based on valid evidence. Thus, conceptually, the ability to think critically is closely related to an individual's ability to collect, analyze, and make decisions. The activities of data collection, data analysis, and decision-making are closely related to scientific activities. Therefore, critical thinking dramatically influences a person's success in learning Science and carrying out scientific activities. However, empirical data that clearly states this is needed.

In real life, someone can conduct data collection, analysis, and decision-making activities through reading. It means that reading activities are also closely related to critical thinking. Sanusi & Prasetyo (2019), Riana (2021), and Bashir (2022) state that reading plays an important role in everyday life as a way of obtaining information, data, and other knowledge. More specifically, Toruan et al. (2022) say that the ability to read will form the ability to make analyses and lead to the right decisions. Therefore, reading activities can give someone broad insight, deep knowledge, and accurate data so they can make the right decisions in their life. In other words, reading activities are directly or indirectly scientific activities.

Reading is the most fundamental scientific activity for students; it must be one of the reading activities that receive the most excellent attention from teachers. As a scientific activity, reading is, of course, closely related to scientific literacy abilities. Therefore, people with good reading skills are believed to have good scientific literacy skills. However, unfortunately, the reading skills of students in Indonesia tend not to support the development of scientific literacy skills. Teachers' efforts to encourage students to read various learning sources must be carried out consistently, especially in reading explanatory texts. Through reading explanatory texts, students gain many benefits, including developing insight and critical thinking skills.

Regarding reading activities, Totok (2019) and Latif et al. (2022) believe that one of the reasons for the low scientific literacy of students in Indonesia is their low reading ability. Research by Restuningsih et al. (2017) shows an effect of interaction between critical thinking skills and interest in reading on reading ability. People with critical thinking skills tend to have a good interest in reading and good critical reading skills. Apart from that, Riana (2021) also found that students with critical thinking skills tend to have critical reading skills. The research results of Nurul & Puri (2023) also found a positive correlation between a moderate or sufficient level of interpretation between reading habits and critical thinking skills. Unfortunately, these studies are still in the "Indonesian" subject arena, so their contribution to increasing scientific literacy is still relatively low. Considering that scientific

literacy skills are closely related to critical thinking skills, the question arises: Does the reading process of students in Indonesia not involve critical thinking skills?

Unfortunately, there has not been much research on the influence of CTS on the reading process and comprehension of texts, especially Science explanatory texts. Therefore, this research seeks to see the extent of the influence of STS on understanding science explanation texts, especially in the context of junior high school science learning. Research is fundamental to carry out as a consideration for Indonesian language teachers and science teachers to develop models and learning techniques with more appropriate approaches so that students' language skills and scientific literacy can be developed together. Apart from that, existing research needs to convey how strong and convincing the relationship is between reading skills and critical thinking skills, so it still needs to be researched in more depth.

Apart from reading and critical thinking skills, another factor that has influenced students' relatively low scientific literacy is Metacognition. Metacognition is closely related to a person's ability to understand how his mind works, including awareness and control over the cognitive processes (Rambe, 2020). Anggo (2012), Hacker et al. (2015), Rhodes (2019), and Beach et al. (2020) explain that Metacognition is related to a person's awareness of their thinking and the ability to organize their thinking in learning or solving problems. More clearly, Yeung & Summerfield (2012), Asy'ari et al. (2018), and Teng (2023) state that metacognitive ability is a high-level thinking ability consisting of (1) knowledge about cognition (metacognitive knowledge) and (2) metacognitive awareness, namely a person's ability to reflect, understand and control their learning, including metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation. Therefore, it can be understood that Metacognition is closely related to the ability to think, organize thinking, and solve problems while reading and science activities are closely related to these abilities.

Several studies have proven that metacognitive abilities positively affect students' learning outcomes. Some of these studies were conducted by Kemalawati et al. (2019), and Anindya et al. (2019), who found that Metacognition influences mastery of science concepts, Metacognition also influences improving English language test results (Teng & Yang, 2022). Ulichusna et al. (2019) and LaCaille et al. (2019) found that Metacognition positively affected students' activeness in attending lessons. Kim (2019) in his research found that Metacognition has a positive effect on a person's emotional intelligence and leadership attitudes. Humairah (2020) found that Metacognition influences problem-solving abilities. Therefore, it can be said that empirically, Metacognition has a vital role in supporting students' learning processes and outcomes.

Even though Metacognition is theoretically and empirically closely related to reading activities and science activities and has been proven to be essential in supporting students' learning processes and outcomes, much research still needs to be conducted that connects and tests how far Metacognition influences reading activities and understanding. The text they read. Thus, indirectly, the results of the research above do not yet answer how strong the influence of Metacognition is on students' learning processes and outcomes, making it possible to develop models, teaching materials, and learning media that are oriented toward successful mastery of concepts (increasing scientific literacy) by taking into account metacognitive abilities. Learners. Therefore, further research needs to be carried out to answer this Problem.

Referring to the urgency of scientific literacy skills and the various efforts to improve them in Indonesia, which tend to be less than optimal, this research seeks to contribute to efforts to explore students' potential, especially in terms of reading skills, critical thinking skills, Metacognition and looking at their influence on understanding explanatory texts, in the context of science learning. This effort is essential for developing the ability to read and understand science-explanatory texts. A good understanding of Science explanatory texts can encourage increased scientific literacy skills.

The subjects "Indonesian" and Science have several similarities and differences. From the point of view of the form of teaching materials, the two subjects have similarities, namely consisting of explanatory texts; however, from the point of view of substance, they have apparent differences and orientations. Indonesian language lessons tend to be social, while science lessons are exact. Thus, it can be understood that the types of explanatory texts in the two subjects have many differences. From a student's perspective, science lessons are generally more complex than "Indonesian" subjects. In Indonesian language and science lessons, reading, critical thinking, and Metacognition are needed. However, research needs to show how reading skills, critical thinking skills, and Metacognition influence the understanding of explanatory texts in the context of science learning. Therefore, this research has an essential position in answering this Problem.

2. Method

This research uses a quantitative approach, which uses numbers, from data collection to interpreting and presenting the results (Priadana & Denok Sunarsi, 2021). Presenting results in pictures, tables, graphs, or other representative displays can increase reader absorption and make it easier to convey information. The data in this research was collected through tests conducted on students at the junior high school level. Each instrument is prepared and developed by referring to the indicators for each variable that have been put forward by experts previously.

The population in this study were junior high school students in Jambi City with an Islamic school base, namely the Integrated Islamic Middle School (SMPIT) and Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs), with a total of 16 schools. It is done with the consideration that samples are obtained from schools with the same characteristics or tend to be the same so that data bias can be reduced. The number of samples used in this research was 136 people in class VIII. Thus, they are generally in the same age range, so their emotional maturity is relatively similar. Sampling was carried out using a random sampling technique.

The data used in this research was obtained through questionnaires and tests. The questionnaire consists of questions with answers using a Likert scale. A questionnaire was conducted to measure metacognitive abilities. The variables reading skills (RS), CTS, and Explanatory Text Comprehension are measured using test questions. Each instrument for measuring variables is prepared based on the indicators of each variable. The instruments used in this research are entirely in Indonesian and are kept by the researcher as research documentation.

The data analysis technique was carried out using the Pearson bivariate correlation test. In this research, the test was carried out with the help of SPSS 25. In this research, the tests carried out consisted of (1) testing the correlation between reading skills and understanding science explanation texts, (2) testing the correlation between critical thinking skills and understanding science explanation texts, and (3) testing the correlation between Metacognition and understanding science explanation texts. Apart from that, in this research, a multivariate correlation test was also carried out, namely: (1) correlation test between reading skills and critical thinking skills on understanding science explanation texts, (2) correlation test between reading skills and Metacognition on understanding science explanation texts, (3)) test the correlation between critical thinking skills and Metacognition on understanding science explanation texts, and (4) test the correlation between reading skills, critical thinking and Metacognition on understanding science explanation texts. In more detail, the correlation design of this research can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1: Variable Analysis Pattern

3. Data and Discussion

The data in the research are in the form of student test results in the form of science explanation text reading skills (RS), critical thinking skills (CTS), Metacognition, and a test of understanding the concept of explanation text (ETU). Each variable is measured with a different instrument, according to each indicator. The complete results of each variable are stored as necessary documentation in this research. The statistical results of the correlation between variables using SPSS 25 are presented in detail in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Pearson Bivariate Correlation Test Variables
Correlations

		RS	CTS	Metacognition	ETU Science
RS	Pearson Correlation	1	.547**	.438**	.477**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	136	136	136	136
CTS	Pearson Correlation	.547**	1	.477**	.770**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	136	136	136	136
Metacognition	Pearson Correlation	.438**	.477**	1	.404**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	136	136	136	136
ETU Science	Pearson Correlation	.477**	.770**	.404**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	136	136	136	136

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

1. Test the correlation between reading skills and understanding of science explanation texts

Referring to Table 1 above, it can be seen that the correlation between RS and ETU has a value of $R = 0.477$. The R-value is greater than $T_{Table} = 0.1406$ for $N=36$. In theory, if the correlation test results are $R_{count} > R_{Table}$, then H_a is accepted, meaning there is a correlation between students' reading skills and understanding of science explanation texts. The sig value strengthens the R test results. 0.00, as is the statistical requirement, the sig value is less than 0.05, then H_a is accepted, and H_o is rejected. Therefore, it can be understood that there is a significant correlation between RS and the ETU of students.

Apart from that, based on the data (Table 2 above), it can also be seen that RS is positively correlated with the CTS and metacognition variables, respectively, getting a score of $R=0.547$ and $R=0.438$. The correlation of each variable is also strengthened by sig. $0.00 < 0.05$. It means that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected for the correlation of RS to CTS

and Metacognition, meaning that the positive correlation between these variables is significant.

2. Test the correlation between critical thinking skills and understanding of science explanation texts

The test result data in Table 1 above also shows a correlation between CTS and ETU with a value of $R = 0.770$. The R -value is greater than $T_{Table} = 0.1406$ for $N = 36$. In theory, if the correlation test results are $R_{count} > R_{Table}$, then H_a is accepted, meaning there is a correlation between CTS and students' understanding of science explanation texts. The sig value strengthens the R test results. 0.00 is the statistical requirement; H_a is accepted if the sig value is less than 0.05 . Based on this sig, it can be understood that there is a significant correlation between students' CTS and ETU.

Apart from that, still referring to the data (Table 2 above) shows that CTS is positively correlated with the RS and Metacognition variables, obtaining scores of $R = 0.547$ and $R = 0.477$, respectively. The correlation of each variable is also strengthened by sig. $0.00 < 0.05$. Sig value. It shows that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected for the correlation of CTS with Metacognition and ETU, meaning that the positive correlation between these variables is significant.

3. Test the correlation between Metacognition and understanding of science explanation texts

The following correlation test result is between the Metacognition variable and ETU. The test result data in Table 1 above shows a correlation between Metacognition and ETU with a value of $R = .404^{**}$. The R -value is greater than $T_{Table} = 0.1406$ for $N = 36$. Theoretically, if the correlation test results are $R_{count} > R_{Table}$, then H_a is accepted, meaning there is a correlation between Metacognition and students' understanding of science explanation texts. The sig value strengthens the R test results. 0.00 . As a statistical rule, if the sig value is less than 0.05 , then H_a is accepted. Based on these data, it can be understood that there is a significant correlation between Metacognition and students' ETU.

Still referring to the data (Table 1) above, it can be seen that the three variables RS, CTS, and M, Metacognition, have different levels of correlation, namely 0.477^{**} , 0.770^{**} , and 0.404^{**} , respectively. Even though these three variables significantly affect ETU, they influence the understanding of science explanation texts differently. Among these three variables, the strongest is the CTS variable of 0.770^{**} , followed by the RS variable (0.477) and Metacognition (0.404). This data shows that each variable has a different role and impact on each student.

Next, a multivariate correlation test was conducted to test whether two or more variables influence understanding of science explanation tests. The results of the multivariate correlation statistical test using SPSS 25 on the influence of RS and CTS can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Correlation test between RS and CTS on ETU

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T		Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	22.282	4.279		5.208	.000		
RS	.067	.055	.080	1.217	.226	.701	1.426
CTS	.663	.060	.727	11.062	.000	.701	1.426

a. Dependent Variable: ETU Science

Based on the status test results in Table 2 above, it is known that the coefficient obtained is that the Collinearity Statistics value for Tolerance is $0.701 > 0.10$. The VIF value is $1.426 < 10.0$. Based on this score, a decision can be made that there is no

multicollinearity between the RS and CTS variables on ETU. It means that if the RS and CTS variables are correlated together, there is no correlation. This data also shows that RS and CTS influence the ETU variable independently and not together.

Next, to find out whether the RS and Metacognition variables together influence ETU. The results of statistical tests with SPSS 25 can be seen in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Correlation test between RS and Metacognition on Science ETU

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	45.590	5.192		8.780	.000		
	RS	.312	.069	.372	4.523	.000	.808	1.237
	Metacognition	.191	.065	.241	2.937	.004	.808	1.237

a. Dependent Variable: ETU Science

Based on the status test results in Table 3 above, it is known that the coefficient obtained is that the Collinearity Statistics value for Tolerance is $0.808 > 0.10$. The VIF value is $1,237 < 10.0$. These data show no multicollinearity between the variables RS and Metacognition towards ETU. It means that if the RS and Metacognition variables are correlated together, there is no correlation. This data also shows that RS and Metacognition independently influence the ETU variable.

The next multivariate correlation test determines whether the CTS and Metacognition variables jointly influence ETU. The results of statistical tests with SPSS 25 can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4. Correlation Test between CTS and Metacognition on Science ETU

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	22.261	4.482		4.967	.000		
	Metacognition	.037	.050	.047	.749	.455	.772	1.295
	CTS	.682	.057	.748	11.908	.000	.772	1.295

a. Dependent Variable: ETU Science

Based on the status test results in Table 4 above, it is known that the coefficient obtained is that the Collinearity Statistics value for Tolerance is $0.772 > 0.10$. The VIF value is $1,295 < 10.0$. These data show no multicollinearity between the Metacognition and CTS variables on ETU. It means that if the Metacognition and CTS variables are correlated together, there is no correlation. This data also shows that Metacognition and CTS only influence the ETU variable independently.

The next multivariate correlation test determines whether all variables influence ETU, namely RS, CTS, and Metacognition. The results of statistical tests with SPSS 25 can be seen in Table 5 below:

Table 5. Correlation Test between RS, CTS, and Metacognition on Science ETU

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	21.610	4.522		4.779	.000		
	RS	.061	.057	.072	1.064	.289	.660	1.514
	CTS	.653	.063	.716	10.315	.000	.631	1.585
	Metacognition	.024	.051	.030	.472	.638	.728	1.374

a. Dependent Variable: ETU Science

Based on the status test results in Table 5 above, it is known that the coefficient obtained is that the Collinearity Statistics value for Tolerance for RS is $0.660 > 0.10$, and the VIF value is $1.514 < 10.0$. As for the CTS, the variable is $0.631 > 0.10$, and the VIF value is $1.585 < 10.0$. The metacognition variable is $0.728 > 0.10$, and the VIF value is $1.374 < 10.0$. These data show no multicollinearity between the RS, CTS, and metacognition variables on Science ETU. It means that if the Metacognition and CTS variables are correlated together, there is no correlation. This data also shows that Metacognition and CTS only influence the ETU variable independently.

The test results and correlation tests for the three variables (Table 1) show that the three variables, RS, CTS, and Metacognition, generally correlate positively with understanding explanatory text (UTE) in the context of junior high school science lessons. The level of correlation between the three variables is different, namely 0.477^{**} , 0.770^{**} , and 0.404^{**} , respectively. This fact proves that each variable has different characteristics and effects on students' understanding of explanatory texts. CTS is The most vital variable influencing students' understanding of science explanation texts. The strongest of these three variables is the CTS variable of 0.770^{**} , followed by the RS variable (0.477) and Metacognition (0.404).

The strong influence of CTS on understanding science explanatory texts proves that reading activities require good CTS support to understand the texts they read. The better a person's CTS, the better their reading ability and understanding of reading material (explanatory text). In other words, if the activity of reading an explanatory text is not accompanied by good CTS, the data or information obtained from an explanatory text is not optimal. The results of this research align with research conducted by Riana (2021), which states that good critical reading skills are needed to understand the content of an explanatory text. Restuningsih et al. (2017) state that people with good critical thinking skills tend to be able to read critically and understand the content of the reading better.

Seeing the strong and convincing correlation between the CTS variable and student learning outcomes, especially in terms of understanding the content of reading explanatory texts in the context of science learning, inspires teachers to increase students' ability to understand the content of a text can be done by strengthening students' CTS. Thus, teachers must consciously and systematically strive to increase students' CTS. Indonesian language teachers can make efforts to improve students' CTS, including implementing innovative learning models that can stimulate students' high-level thinking abilities. Several learning modes that have been empirically proven to increase students' CTS are problem-based learning models (Purnaningsih et al., 2019; Ariyanto et al., 2020). A project-based learning model (Permana & Setyawan, 2019) was also implemented in learning.

Implementing the Problem-based Learning and project-based learning models in Indonesian language lessons on the theme of explanatory text with science text media is a breakthrough in efforts to improve the scientific literacy skills of students in Indonesia. Previously, when implementing Indonesian language learning using the Explanatory Text theme, teachers used texts with genres or descriptions of social phenomena. Using explanatory texts with descriptions or genres of natural phenomena (Science) is rarely done and tends to be avoided for various reasons. Apart from that, implementing Problem-based learning and project-based learning models in Indonesian language lessons on the theme of Explanatory Text. Explanatory text learning often focuses on writing and linguistic structures (Apriyani, 2019; Fitriana, 2019; Darlisa et al., 2023), so using these two models is less relevant. Therefore, Indonesian language teachers tend to use other themes in these subjects to increase students' CTS.

The results of this research also show that reading skills (RS) also positively influence students' understanding of explanatory texts in the context of science learning. The statistical test results (Table 1) show that the level of correlation between the two variables is significant in the medium category ($R = 0.477$). This data shows that people with

good reading skills also have a better understanding of the reading content and vice versa. This data aligns with the research results of Andanik and Fitriawanati (2019), who found that reading skills influence reading comprehension and problem-solving abilities, especially in mathematics learning. Thus, teachers need to practice reading explanatory text skills in the context of science learning to improve text comprehension and problem-solving abilities. Understanding and solving abilities can positively impact efforts to improve the scientific literacy abilities of students in Indonesia in general.

This research also finds evidence that Metacognition plays a role in students' ability to understand explanatory texts in the context of science learning. The influence of Metacognition on understanding the content of scientific explanation texts reached 0.404 in the moderate but significant category. This analysis data aligns with the research results of Usman et al. (2018) and Ilma et al. (2022), who found a positive relationship between metacognition and student learning outcomes. Anindya et al. (2019) and McMillan et al. (2022) also found that metacognitive abilities had a positive effect on science learning outcomes, and even Van der Graaf et al. (2022) and Krieger et al. (2022) states that Metacognition influences the skills of thinking, behaving and acting in a more complex manner. Thus, it can be understood that metacognitive abilities play a convincing role in improving learning outcomes. In the context of this research, the learning outcome in question is understanding the content of explanatory texts in science learning.

The urgency of Metacognition on learning outcomes in general and understanding Science explanatory texts, in particular, has implications for new ideas for Indonesian language teachers to actively plan and systematically use Science explanatory texts as learning media and resources. Indonesian language teachers must actively involve students' metacognitive abilities to optimally participate in the learning process and obtain maximum learning results. Kemalawati et al. (2019) and Evivania et al. (2020) advise teachers, including Indonesian language teachers, to be involved in implementing learning and using metacognition-based learning strategies. Teachers must also use metacognition-based learning media to improve students' metacognitive abilities (Hendi et al., 2020). Therefore, teachers must actively study various models, methods, or strategies, including learning media, that can potentially develop students' metacognitive abilities.

The results of this research directly and indirectly also show that the use of Science explanatory texts in Indonesian language learning has the potential to support and improve students' scientific literacy skills in Indonesia. Apart from that, using science explanation texts in Indonesian language learning also makes it possible to improve students' reading skills. It is based on previous findings that one of the reasons why the level of scientific literacy of students in Indonesia is still low is also due to their still low reading ability. If what is meant is the ability to read data, symbols, or scientific notation, then the use of explanatory text can be one of the best alternatives.

Apart from that, the results of this research have also shown the critical role of Indonesian language teachers in increasing students' scientific literacy in Indonesia. Previously, efforts to increase students' scientific literacy in the context of improving rankings on the PISA and TIMSS tests were entirely borne by science teachers. Various teacher trainings to improve scientific literacy skills are focused on science teachers. It is based on the idea that science teachers are the most critical parties in these efforts. However, this research shows that Indonesian language teachers are critical in improving students' scientific literacy skills. Implementing explanatory text learning using science text media is an excellent opportunity to support improving students' scientific literacy skills.

4. Conclusion

Participants showed a relatively positive level of each variable (reading skills, critical thinking skills, Metacognition, and understanding of explanatory text). In addition, a strong correlation was found between reading skills (RS) and critical thinking skills (CTS),

and Metacognitive Ability (MA) was significantly correlated with Explanatory Text Comprehension (PTE). The T-test results show that the correlation of each of these variables is significant. Successively, the correlation between the three variables, namely RS, CTS, and Metacognition, has different levels of correlation, namely 0.477**, 0.770**, and 0.404**, respectively. Therefore, science teachers need to carry out learning that begins with effective and consistent reading activities, provide challenging questions that have the potential to trigger an increase in CTS, and assist in learning planning for students. With increasing challenges, these learning activities can be carried out synchronously and asynchronously. In the future, students will be required to read Science explanatory texts more often in recreational digital environments than in academic digital environments.

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